

Research Paper

Sedimentation rates control trace element composition of sedimentary phosphorites: Anomalously low uranium and cadmium levels in Paleozoic shelly phosphorites from the Baltica Paleobasin

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ABSTRACT

Phosphorites – made up of chemically precipitated authigenic apatite or composed of bioapatitic fossil remains – become enriched in a variety of trace elements such as Rare Earth Elements (REE), Cd, and U during diagenesis. The Cambrian-Ordovician phosphorites of the Baltica Paleobasin that are almost exclusively made up of fossilized remains of phosphatic brachiopod shells are, however, exceptional in this regard, showing abnormally low levels of trace elements. In this study, we examined the depositional environment and the trace elemental composition of the Baltic Paleobasin shelly phosphorites. We show that hydrodynamic conditions during deposition exert control on the trace elemental composition of shelly phosphorites. A combination of high sedimentation rates, redox conditions, and the biogenic origin of the shells led to the depletion of bio-toxic Cd and U relative to other similar phosphorite deposits. Similarly, the concentrations of REE are below the global phosphorites average; however, the shelly phosphorites show a higher degree of Middle Rare Earth Element (MREE) enrichment. These findings have further implications for exploration — phosphorites that contain abundant bioapatite and/or were deposited in areas with high sedimentation rates and oxic conditions are likely less enriched in trace elements.

1. Introduction

Phosphorus (P) is an essential and non-substitutable element for life on Earth, playing a key role in biomolecules and regulating primary productivity over geological timescales (Tyrrell, 1999). Therefore, most of the mined and processed P is used as a fertilizer in agriculture (Obersteiner et al., 2013). Additionally, P is also utilized in various industrial applications, including food processing and energy storage (e.g., Pufahl and Groat, 2017). The primary phosphate-containing phase in phosphorites is apatite — a calcium phosphate mineral with the generalized formula of $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH}, \text{F}, \text{Cl})$, whereas in carbonate-rich fluids (e.g., marine porewaters), the thermodynamically stable phase is carbonate-rich fluorapatite (CFap; Jahnke, 1984). Due to its complex crystal structure, a wide variety of elements can substitute in the apatite structure for Ca (e.g., K, Mn, Ni, Cu, Co, Zn, Sr, Pb, Cd, Y and REE) and for PO_4^{3-} (e.g., AsO_4^{3-} , SO_4^{2-} , VO_4^{3-} , CrO_4^{2-}) (Pan and Fleet, 2002). Some of these substitutions can have significant industrial implications, with

either beneficial or detrimental effects. For example, long-term use of P-fertilizers produced from trace metal-rich (e.g., Cd, As, U) ores can contaminate agricultural soils and groundwater (Kratz and Schnug, 2006), with significant adverse health outcomes directly related to the use of P-based agrochemicals (e.g., Jayasumana et al., 2015). Conversely, phosphorites also readily take up Rare Earth Elements (REE), and some deep-sea muds rich in biogenic calcium phosphate, show exceptional enrichment, with $\sum\text{REE}$ values reaching >0.5 wt% (Kato et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2024a). In deep-sea muds, apatitic grains can show $\sum\text{REE}$ concentrations of 10,000–30,000 mg/kg (Ren et al., 2022), around two orders of magnitude higher than in average phosphorites (Altschuler, 1980). This type of hyper-enrichment has been interpreted as the result of prolonged uptake of bottom seawater or porewater sourced REE near the seawater-sediment interface (SWI) under extremely low sedimentation rates (Bi et al., 2021; Deng et al., 2022; Huang et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023; Paul et al., 2019; Ren et al., 2022; Takaya et al., 2018). REE-enriched phosphorite deposits could be

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considered a potential ore for these economically critical elements (Emsbo et al., 2015; Takaya et al., 2018). However, most of the phosphorites are also significantly enriched in several potentially toxic heavy metals with enrichment factors as high as 60 for Cd and 30 for U compared to average sedimentary rocks (Jarvis et al., 1994). While it is well established that the degree of enrichment varies significantly between different phosphorite deposits (Altschuler, 1980; Bech et al., 2010), little effort has been made to study the geochemical causes of trace metal variability in phosphorites, especially of potentially toxic metals (e.g., Nathan et al., 1997).

Phosphorites and sedimentary phosphates can form in a range of depositional environments, from peritidal inner shelves at continental margins to open ocean carbonate-reef atolls (Föllmi, 1996; Pufahl and Groat, 2017). Similarly, there can be significant differences in trace elemental abundances in different phosphorites, for example, REE concentrations can differ by up to three orders of magnitude in different deposits, with some authors attributing this difference to temporal variability of dissolved REE in seawater (Emsbo et al., 2015). On the other hand, there seems to be a link between depositional environments and trace elemental abundances (Filippelli, 2011). In Recent Namibian

Fig. 1. (A) Paleogeographic reconstruction showing the location of the Baltica paleocontinent during the Ordovician. (B) Distribution of Cambrian-Ordovician organic-rich shales (dashed lines) and sandstones (yellow) on the Baltica paleocontinent. Grid pattern indicates land (C) Map of the study area. Red dots indicate drill cores used for geochemical analyses. Data from Estonian Land Board (2024), Heinsalu (1986), Müller et al. (2018), Schovsbo et al. (2018), and Popov et al. (2019). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

phosphorites, REE concentrations are higher in middle-to-outer shelf phosphorite grains than in similar grains from the inner shelf (Lumiste et al., 2019). Likewise, there is systematic variation in the concentration of Cd and other biotoxic elements in contemporaneous phosphorite layers of the North American Phosphoria Formation, with lower concentrations found in the layers deposited in nearshore settings (Hiatt and Budd, 2003).

Most economic sedimentary phosphate deposits worldwide are primarily made of either pristine or reworked apatite lithofacies sediments (sensu Föllmi et al., 1991) composed of (potentially microbially mediated) chemically precipitated apatite particles and nodules, phosphatized substrates and laminas (Arning et al., 2009a, 2009b; Mänd et al., 2018; Schulz and Schulz, 2005). A less significant phosphatic phase in these deposits is represented by biogenic apatite, such as bones and teeth of vertebrates, coprolites and other skeletal remains of apatite-secreting animals (Garmit et al., 2017; Kocsis et al., 2016; Lécuyer et al., 2004). Dissimilarly, significant phosphate rock deposits are found in the Cambrian-Ordovician sandstones of the Baltic Paleobasin in the northern East European Platform in Estonia and northwestern Russia (Fig. 1b) which are almost exclusively made up of biogenic apatite. In these deposits, the dominant apatite phase consists of phosphatic shells of extinct lingulate brachiopods (Lang and Puura, 2013; Lang et al., 2016). Linguliform brachiopods (Fig. 2a) differ from most other marine invertebrates by using apatite instead of carbonate to construct their shells (Williams and Cusack, 1999). The brachiopod shells contain up to 35–37 wt% P_2O_5 , and the shallow marine peritidal shelly phosphatic sandstones deposited in the Baltic Paleobasin can, at times, contain shell

detritus constituting up to 90 % of the rock volume with a typical whole rock P_2O_5 concentrations ranging from 6 to 20 wt% (Baturin and Ilyin, 2013; Raudsep, 1997). Similar phosphatic brachiopod coquina beds are found in lower Paleozoic siliciclastic sediments deposited in near-shore settings in Sweden (Puura and Holmer, 1993), SW Europe and North Africa (Cocks and Popov, 2021; Emig and Gutiérrez-Marco, 1997; Romano et al., 1986) and South America (Aceñolaza et al., 2003). Linguliform brachiopods typically have a low preservation potential in sedimentary systems (Kowalewski, 1996), and the late Cambrian–early Ordovician sandstones with abundant linguliform phosphatic brachiopods in Estonia and NW Russia form the only shelly phosphorite deposit with economic significance. Moreover, the shelly phosphorites of the Baltic Basin are typified by their remarkably low trace element (including REE + Y) content (Lécuyer et al., 2004; Lumiste et al., 2021a).

In this contribution, we study (i) the trace elemental composition of the shelly phosphorite ore of the Baltic Paleobasin, focusing on potentially hazardous trace elements and the REE, and (ii) constrain the causes of the anomalously low trace element concentrations in these deposits. We propose that the shelly phosphorites are severely depleted in trace elements due to a combination of the biogenic origin of the apatite, causing low initial concentrations coupled with exceptionally high sedimentation rates, leading to short diagenetic uptake time.

2. Geological setting

The shelly phosphorites were deposited in a shallow epicontinental sea - called the Baltic Paleobasin - during the Cambrian-Ordovician

Fig. 2. Photographs of (A) a phosphatic brachiopod shell of *Ungula ingrira*, (B) bulk phosphorite rock containing abundant brachiopod shells. Optical plane-polarized photographs of (C) a brachiopod coquina (*Obolus conglomerate*) and (D) phosphatic detritus of the Kallavere Formation. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) back-scattered electron images of (E, F) apatitic brachiopod shells intergrown with micrometer-sized authigenic pyrite. Q — quartz, Ap — apatite, Py — pyrite.

transition (Fig. 1a; Ilyin and Heinsalu, 1990). The Baltic Paleobasin was located at the present-day southern margins of the Fennoscandian Shield, positioned at 40–50° southernly latitudes (Cocks and Torsvik, 2005) in Cambrian to Early Ordovician. It is bordered by the Ural orogenic belt from the east, by the Caledonian Front from the northwest and by the Teisseyre-Tornquist Zone from the southwest (Harris et al., 2004; Nikishin et al., 1996). In the northern part of the Baltic Paleobasin, sedimentary succession ranges from the Ediacaran to the Devonian. During the Furongian and Early Ordovician, the Baltic Paleobasin was a passive margin with a meridionally west-facing shoreline likely influenced by upwelling (Torsvik et al., 2012; Vind et al., 2023). Under these conditions, enhanced delivery of nutrients from the deep ocean led to a significant build-up of organic matter and marine biota, evidenced by the presence of extensive organic-rich black shale deposits spanning from present-day Norway to northwestern Russia and phosphatic brachiopod shell beds that range from northwestern Estonia to Lake Ladoga region (Nielsen and Schovsbo, 2011; Popov et al., 1989). Throughout the Phanerozoic, the northern Baltic Paleobasin was marked by tectonic quiescence with no indication of large-scale tectonic or metamorphic events, except local scale faulting (Puura and Vaher, 1997).

Phosphatic linguliform brachiopods appear in the Estonian sedimentary succession in the uppermost Cambrian Furongian Stage Ülgase and Tsitre Formations' (Fig. 3) sandstones, where four brachiopod zones have been distinguished – *Ungula inornata* Zone, *Ungula convexa* Zone, *Ungula ingrlica* Zone, and *Obolus apollinis* Zone, the latter reaching the Tremadocian Stage in the lowermost Ordovician (Popov et al., 1989; Puura and Holmer, 1993). The phosphatic brachiopods are the most abundant in the quartzose sandstones of the Kallavere Formation (Figs. 3, 4), where the Cambrian-Ordovician boundary is biostratigraphically defined at the base of the *Cordylodus lindströmi* conodont Zone (Heinsalu and Viira, 1997; Meidla, 2017).

The thickness of the Kallavere Formation ranges from 1 to 17 m, covering most of Estonia (Heinsalu and Viira, 1997). The Kallavere sandstones outcrop to the surface in northern Estonia, but due to the southward dipping of the homoclinally bedded Paleozoic sediments, the burial depth of the Kallavere sandstones increases southward by 2–3 m/km. The thickness of the overburden exceeds 500 m in southern Estonia (Raudsep, 1997). In the Rakvere, Toolse, and Aseri areas, the thickness of the Kallavere Formation ranges from 1 to 12 m, and the overburden increases from 5 m in the northernmost Toolse deposit to approximately 200 m at the southern margin of the Rakvere deposit (Raudsep, 1997).

The Kallavere Formation consists of friable to weakly cemented yellow to grey cross-bedded quartzose sandstones with a variable

content of phosphatic shell detritus. Black shale interlayers occasionally occur in the formation's upper parts (Heinsalu and Viira, 1997). The dominant species of phosphatic brachiopods found in the sandstones is *Ungula ingrlica*, alongside shells belonging to the genera *Schmidtites*, *Keyserlingia*, and *Oepikites* (Heinsalu and Viira, 1997). Besides the shells, apatite-cemented quartz sand clasts and diagenetic pore-filling cements occur (Lumiste et al., 2021a), and both the shells and clasts contain abundant diagenetic pyrite or hematite (Lang et al., 2016). The shells and phosphatic clasts show signs of variable degrees of reworking and winnowing, forming lens-like discontinuous phosphate-rich coquina beds throughout the formation (Heinsalu et al., 1994).

Low Conodont Alteration Index values (CAI = 1) coupled with low subsidence rates in the northern part of the Baltica paleocontinent (Heinsalu et al., 2003; Kirsimäe and Jørgensen, 2000) point towards the relatively pristine condition of these phosphorites. Phosphate $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of around 15–17 ‰ measured in Kallavere formation brachiopod shells suggest seawater and/or porewater paleotemperatures of <40 °C (Lécuyer et al., 1998) further supporting low-temperature post-depositional conditions for these sediments. Therefore, the shelly phosphorites are unlikely to have gone through any large-scale remobilization of trace elements (i.e., hydrothermal resetting).

The shelly phosphorite of the Baltic Paleobasin was mined in Estonia from the 1920s to 1991 in the Ülgase and Maardu deposits. In the 1950s, extensive shelly phosphorite beds were discovered in northern Estonia (Raudsep, 1997). Exploration from the 1950s to the 1980s recognized three large phosphorite deposits — Rakvere, Toolse and Aseri — with estimated resources of 1938 (11 % P₂O₅), 644 (9 % P₂O₅) and 312 (8 % P₂O₅) million tons of phosphate rock, respectively (Estonian Mineral Registry, 2024). However, the exploration was stopped in 1989, and no mining operations commenced due to technological, environmental and socio-economic issues (Adamson et al., 1997; Raudsep, 1997). The exploration of phosphorite was restarted by the Geological Survey of Estonia in 2018 (Joosu et al., 2023).

3. Material and methods

Decimeter-scale sedimentological descriptions were made for 23 drill cores from the Rakvere, Toolse, and Aseri deposits (Fig. 1c). Additionally, concentrations of P across the phosphorite intervals of the new cores were scanned with a Bruker 5i hand-held X-ray fluorescence spectrometer at 10 or 20-cm intervals.

For the geochemical analysis, two different sample sets were used for this study: (i) an archive sample set from drill cores collected during the 20th-century exploration campaigns, and (ii) samples extracted from

Fig. 3. Upper Cambrian and lower Ordovician stratigraphy of Estonia. Modified after Meidla et al. (2014).

Fig. 4. Characteristic lithostratigraphic columns of the drillcores from Toolse, Aseri and Rakvere deposits with hand-held XRF scanned P₂O₅ concentrations. For the location of the cores, see Fig. 1.

new drill cores drilled in 2020 and 2021 (Fig. 1c; Joosu et al., 2023). Archive samples were collected by continuous sampling of the whole cores at typically 50 to 100 cm intervals. A similar methodology was employed for sampling the new cores, where an 83 mm-diameter core was halved, and one-half of the phosphate-containing Kallavere Formation was continuously sampled at 50 to 100 cm intervals, depending on the heterogeneity of the phosphorite-bearing sediments. The collected samples were crushed, powdered, and divided into subsamples for subsequent major and trace element analyses.

The major and trace element concentrations of phosphorites from new cores were analyzed at ALS Minerals Loughrea. Major element and oxide concentrations were determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) from Li-borate fused beads. Trace elemental composition of the samples was determined by either (i) Li-borate fusion, acid digestion and ICP-MS or (ii) four acid digestion and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES). AMIS0055, AMIS0250, AMIS0304, OREAS 102a, 602, 905 and 920 reference materials were used for quality control. The total sulfur concentrations were determined by LECO Infrared Spectroscopy.

Geochemical analysis of the archive samples was performed at the University of Tartu. For analysis, 0.2 g of the sample was digested in 10 ml of *aqua regia* at 180 °C for 35 min, using a microwave-assisted digestion system. The resulting solutions were diluted with 2 % HNO₃ and measured using an Agilent 8800 quadrupole ICP-MS/MS. Indium was used as an internal standard element, and NIST 1640a, NIST 1643f and POLC-1 standards were used for quality control.

In-situ microscale mapping of phosphorites was performed with laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) using an Agilent 8800 quadrupole ICP-MS coupled to a Cetac LSX- 213 G2+ laser with an HeEx II fast-washout two-volume large-format cell. The mapping parameters were as follows: 20 μm, 10 μm/s, 10 Hz and 1.3 J/cm², for spot size, scan speed, frequency and fluence, respectively. During LA-ICP-MS analysis, the formation rates of Ba- and LREE- oxides, which can interfere with Eu and HREE signals, were monitored using Th-oxide formation. ThO/Th values remained below 0.25 % throughout the entire analytical session.

The REE concentrations were normalized against PAAS (Post Archean Australian Shale standard, Taylor and McLennan, 1985) and denoted by the subscript “N”. REE anomalies were calculated using a linear method after Bau and Dulski (1996) and Shields and Stille (2001) and the bell-shape index (BSI) after Tostevin et al. (2016).

The measured elements and oxides, as well as their detection limits, are reported in Supplementary Table 1. The relative standard deviation of duplicate analysis of reference materials, was <5 % for all reported elements in both datasets. Analytical accuracy, expressed as the difference between measured and reported concentrations of certified reference materials was 95–105 % for newly collected samples and 90–110 % for the archive samples.

4. Results

Representative sedimentological logs of the three deposits are depicted in Fig. 4, and P₂O₅ and trace element concentrations of the studied samples are shown in Supplementary Table 1.

The Kallavere Formation is characterized by cross-bedded fine to medium, occasionally coarse-grained, quartz arenite sandstones deposited in shallow marine to shore-face/beach high-energy conditions. The formation bears locally abundant fossil remains of phosphatic linguliform brachiopods that occur as lens-like accumulations of complete valves (coquinas) or brachiopod detritus of varying grain sizes and amounts (Fig. 2). Abundance of phosphatic shells in Kallavere Formation varies significantly both stratigraphically and laterally. In the northern part of the studied area, in Toolse and Aseri deposits, the content of phosphatic detritus is highest at the base of the formation and shows an upward decrease along with the fining sandstone grain size and appearance of thin black shale interbeds (Fig. 4). In the south, in

Rakvere deposit, the lower part of the Kallavere Formation composed of fine-to-medium-grained sandstone with thin black-shale is low in phosphatic detritus (10–20 %), and opposite to Toolse and Aseri deposits, the brachiopod detritus content and grain size increase upward, forming tens of centimetres thick coquina beds with shell content as high as 70 %.

The variation in the abundance of shells is also reflected in P₂O₅ content, showing different stratigraphic trends in studied deposits. In the Rakvere deposit, the highest P₂O₅ concentrations reaching up to 25 wt% are found in the upper parts of the Kallavere Formation, whereas the concentrations increase towards the footwall in the Toolse and Aseri deposits (Fig. 4). SiO₂ concentrations show an opposite trend, with higher values occurring in low-P intervals. Average Cd concentrations are 0.04 mg/kg (n = 51; concentrations in all 166 samples analyzed from the novel cores were below the detection limit of 0.5 mg/kg). Average U concentrations are 16.3 (SD = 10.8, n = 123), 23.6 (SD = 10.5, n = 31), and 20.9 mg/kg (SD = 7.8, n = 63) in the Rakvere, Aseri, and Toolse deposits, respectively. Th is present at low concentration in the shelly phosphorites, with average concentrations ranging from 2.5 mg/kg in Rakvere (SD = 0.86, n = 123) to 3.7 mg/kg in Toolse (SD = 1.21, n = 63) deposit. Sr concentrations range from 57 to 3590 mg/kg in the studied samples, with the highest average concentration (1205 mg/kg, SD = 868.2, n = 123) found in the Rakvere deposit. Except for U and Sr, most of these elements show weak-to-no correlation with P₂O₅ (Fig. 5). S concentrations are low throughout the Rakvere deposit, with values ranging from 0.02 to 1.1 wt%, with an average of 0.08 wt% (SD = 0.13 n = 78). In the Toolse and Aseri deposits, the average S concentrations are somewhat higher – 1.15 (SD = 0.89, n = 57) and 1.28 (SD = 0.87, n = 31), respectively.

REE concentrations in the shelly phosphorites differ between the Rakvere and the two other deposits, with average concentrations of 273 (SD = 76.8, n = 123), compared to 368 (SD = 170.8, n = 63) and 366 mg/kg (SD = 221.4, n = 31) in the Toolse and Aseri, respectively. However, the inter-elemental REE composition of the shelly phosphorites is similar throughout all the studied deposits, with REE + Y patterns showing slight MREE-enrichment (Fig. 6). Correlations between P₂O₅ and ∑REE also differ between deposits (Fig. 7). In Toolse and Aseri, ∑REE strongly correlates with P₂O₅ concentrations, with Pearson correlation coefficient values of 0.95 (p < 0.05) and 0.9 (p < 0.05) for the Toolse and Aseri, respectively. On the other hand, in the Rakvere deposit samples, the correlation is significantly weaker (r = 0.53, p < 0.05).

The in-situ data show the heterogeneous distribution of trace elements within the phosphorite (Fig. 8). The REE are dominantly concentrated within the external layers of the brachiopod shells. U shows lamellae-like distribution in the inner and outer parts of the shells, whereas pyrite-hosted trace elements are located in discrete pyrite aggregates throughout the sediment as well as in dispersed pyrite within the porous layers of the brachiopod shells.

5. Discussion

5.1. Trace element composition of the shelly phosphorites

The primary P-containing mineral in sedimentary phosphorite – apatite – is susceptible to a wide range of chemical substitutions (Pan and Fleet, 2002), some of which may increase (e.g., REE) or decrease (e.g., U, Th, Cd) the economic potential of the ore. In addition, several of the bio-toxic elements found in phosphorites are not directly associated with apatite but are, instead, found in accessory minerals, mainly in pyrite, which is typically enriched in Cd, Zn, Cu, and Pb (Altschuler, 1980; Jarvis et al., 1994; Pufahl and Groat, 2017). Concentrations of potentially harmful elements can vary significantly between different deposits and even within a single locality (Ahmed et al., 2022; Al-Hwaiti et al., 2005; Aydin et al., 2010; Baioumy, 2005; Nathan et al., 1997). However, the shelly phosphorite of Baltic Paleobasin, which is characterized by low trace element concentrations, is in stark contrast with

Fig. 5. Biplots of P_2O_5 and (A) U, (B) Th, (C) Sr, (D) Cd, (E) As and (F) Pb in different deposits. Note that the y- and x-axis are in different units.

other phosphorites (Fig. 9).

Sedimentary phosphorites are typically enriched in Cd, with concentrations ranging from 2 to 116 mg/kg (Altschuler, 1980; Bech et al., 2010). Cd is a bio-toxic element that has significant adverse effects on human health, and the use of P-fertilizers accounts for around 50 % of the total environmental input of Cd (De Meeùs et al., 2002). In the Estonian shelly phosphorites, however, the concentrations of Cd are several orders of magnitude lower than in other sedimentary phosphorites (Fig. 9). Anomalously low Cd concentration in Estonian shelly phosphorite compared to typical sedimentary phosphates likely stems from different formational pathways and diagenetic environments of authigenic (chemically precipitated) and biogenic apatite. Under conventional phosphogenic conditions (i.e., upwelling and related high rates of bioproduction), Cd is heavily enriched in porewater near the seawater-sediment interface (SWI; Segovia-Zavala et al., 1998), where authigenic apatite primarily precipitates (Schulz and Schulz, 2005). Divalent Cd has a similar ionic radius to Ca^{2+} and, therefore, is readily incorporated into the apatite crystal structure during apatite precipitation and/or subsequent diagenesis (Pan and Fleet, 2002). Alternatively,

Cd-enrichment in phosphorites is related to the presence of diagenetic sulfides (Nathan et al., 1997) and/or organic matter (Ilyin and Kiperman, 2001). Regardless of the specific host phase, Cd-enrichment is biogenic in origin and related to a high influx of dissolved phosphate and other nutrients (Jarvis et al., 1994). Dissimilar to authigenic apatite, the bioapatite in brachiopods is secreted by animals during their lifetime in (quasi)equilibrium with seawater (Lécuyer et al., 1996; Peek and Clementz, 2012) and contains very low levels of trace elements (e.g., $\sum REE < 1$ mg/kg; Lécuyer et al., 1998). Modern linguliform brachiopods inhabit well-oxygenated waters, whereas Cd-enrichment occurs in the seawater column in oxygen-minimum zones (Janssen et al., 2014) and in shallow marine sediments influenced by sulfate reduction and free H_2S (Böning et al., 2004). The brachiopods that make up the Estonian shelly phosphorites were unlikely to inhabit environments enriched with Cd, leading to muted *in vivo* uptake. Further, *post-mortem* deposition of the shells in oxygenated peritidal-shoreface settings with low porewater Cd levels limited the diagenetic uptake of Cd, leading to exceptionally low Cd concentrations in shelly phosphorite.

Authigenic enrichment of U is characteristic of reduced sediments

Fig. 6. PAAS-normalized REE + Y patterns of samples from (A) Aseri, (B) Rakvere, and (C) Toolse deposits, (D) compared to other similar deposits of the world. Data for (D) showing typical REE patterns for various sedimentary phosphorites worldwide and deep-sea muds, from [Ahmed et al. \(2022\)](#), [Emsbo et al. \(2015\)](#) and [Ren et al. \(2022\)](#).

Fig. 7. Biplot of P_2O_5 and ΣREE in Estonian phosphorites. The Rakvere deposit samples show an apparent decoupling of enrichment in P_2O_5 and REE above the PAAS values (ΣREE 183 mg/kg).

where it accumulates via the reduction of soluble U(VI) to the insoluble U(IV) ([Barnes and Cochran, 1990](#)). However, U is also a common trace/minor element in apatite, occupying Ca^{2+} sites as U^{4+} in the apatite structure and apatite may be a significant sink for U in phosphogenetic

sediments ([Lumiste et al., 2021b](#)). Therefore, phosphorites can be, compared to average shales, enriched in U by a factor of >30 , with average concentrations of 120 mg/kg ([Altschuler, 1980](#); [Jarvis et al., 1994](#)). During the production of P-fertilizers, around 80–90 % of U in the ore remains in the fertilizer product ([Kratz and Schnug, 2006](#)). Therefore, long-term usage of phosphate fertilizer can lead to significant accumulation of U in agricultural soils, especially if U-enriched ore is used for fertilizer production ([Sun et al., 2020a, 2020b](#)). Like in the case of Cd, the concentrations of U are relatively low in Estonian shelly phosphorite, with average concentrations ranging from 16.3 mg/kg (SD = 10.8, $n = 123$) in Rakvere to 23.6 mg/kg (SD = 10.5, $n = 31$) in Aseri ([Fig. 5a](#)) indicating low porewater U concentrations during diagenesis, further supporting the interpretation that the depositional settings controlled trace element levels in shelly phosphorites. Furthermore, the U and P_2O_5 show relatively poor covariation, particularly in the Toolse deposit ([Fig. 5a](#)), most probably due to numerous U- and V-rich black shale interlayers in the upper part of the Kallavere Formation and in the overlying Türisalu formation ([Vind et al., 2023](#)).

The concentrations of other potentially toxic elements are at the same level (As, Sr, Pb) or significantly lower (Cu, Cr, Co, Zn) in the shelly phosphorite compared with the global average phosphorite ([Fig. 9](#)). These elements can be, at least to some degree, incorporated into the crystal structure of apatite ([Pan and Fleet, 2002](#)). However, excluding Sr, the low correlation between P_2O_5 and these elements in Estonian shelly phosphorites ([Fig. 5d-f](#)) indicates that they are not primarily found in apatite. On the other hand, many of these elements show strong correlations with S, especially As ($r = 0.93$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 166$), Pb ($r = 0.89$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 166$) and Cu ($r = 0.72$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 166$), indicating that these elements are primarily carried by pyrite.

Besides potentially harmful trace metals, phosphorites also contain

Fig. 8. Backscattered scanning electron microscope image of dolomite cemented bulk phosphorite sample and element distribution maps generated by LA-ICP-MS scanning of P, S, Mg, Ce, Pb, U, Ni, Cu and Zn. All scales are in counts per second (cps). Ap – apatitic shells, Q - quartz, Dol - dolomite, Py – pyrite, R – Ti-oxide.

significant quantities of REE, which are critical elements for a wide range of industries, ranging from green energy technologies to the defense sector (Humphries, 2011). Similar to other trace metals, REE enrichment is highly variable between different phosphate rock deposits of the world, with \sum REE values ranging from <30 to >5000 mg/kg (Ahmed et al., 2022; Emsbo et al., 2015; Valetich et al., 2022). In

Estonian shelly phosphorite rock, the average concentration of REE is 273 (SD = 76.8, n = 123), 368 (SD = 170.8, n = 63) and 366 mg/kg (SD = 221.4, n = 31) for Rakvere, Toulse and Aseri deposits, respectively. A particular feature of the diagenetic uptake of REE by apatite is the enrichment in middle REE (MREE — Nd, Sm, Eu, Tb, and Dy) (Reynard et al., 1999; Fig. 6) indicated by increased BSI values expressing the

Fig. 9. Spider diagram showing the trace element composition of Estonian phosphorite compared to the global average phosphorite. Data for global average phosphorite from Altschuler (1980) and REE-rich deep-sea muds from Bi et al. (2021), Ren et al. (2022), Wang et al. (2024b).

MREE enrichment over LREE and HREE (Tostevin et al., 2016), ranging from 1.3 to 2.2 in the Kallavere Formation phosphorite.

The in-situ data reveal the presence of discrete S-phases and apatite-hosted pyrite (Fig. 8). Trace elements that correlate with sulfur in the bulk samples are also spatially associated, indicating that these elements are dominantly found in pyrite. REE and U are, on the other hand, dominantly found within apatite. Notably, different parts of the shells show the highest degrees of REE and U enrichment – REEs are dominantly found in the outermost layers of the shells, whereas U is found in more porous interlayers throughout the lamellar shell structure. This mismatch in distribution can be explained by the different diagenetic pathways of the brachiopod shell structures. The lamellar phosphatic brachiopod shells consist of closely packed apatite crystallites intercalated by porous apatitic layers that are more prone to diagenetic alteration and recrystallization (Lang et al., 2016). The U is dominantly found within diagenetically altered porous layers formed by the breakdown of mineral-reinforced organic matrices, whereas the REE are found within layers of closely packed apatite nanometer-sized crystals with high surface area (Lumiste et al., 2021a). However, variation in the REE concentrations has not resulted in any significant fractionation and the internal and external parts of a single shell exhibit similar REE + Y patterns (Lumiste et al., 2021a).

5.2. Diagenetic control on the uptake of trace elements

With a few exceptions, like Mg and Sr, which are abundant in seawater, bioapatite does not readily incorporate trace elements in vivo (Trotter and Eggins, 2006), and most of the trace element uptake in bioapatite occurs *post-mortem*. The diagenetic enrichment of trace elements by apatite is governed by the availability of these elements in seawater and/or sediment pore fluid. Trace metals are delivered to the sediment by sinking particles or diffusion from the overlying water column and can be redistributed in the sediment depending on the redox environment (e.g., Tribouillard et al., 2006, 2012). Therefore, the uptake of trace elements is directly related to redox conditions, water mass chemistry, sedimentation rates, organic and inorganic particulate shuttles and the size of the oceanic trace element budgets (Liu and Algeo, 2020).

Furthermore, the Kallavere Formation is primarily represented by sandstone facies, indicating deposition in high-energy nearshore conditions ranging from peri-tidal to distal lower shoreface – offshore environment characterized by very fine-grained to fine-grained sandstone with black-shale and/or silt-to-mudstone interlayers, and cross-bedded sandstones reflecting deposition by storm events. More importantly, Kowalewski (1996) studied the preservation and fossilization of

the modern lingulide brachiopod *Glottidia palmeri* from Baja California, Mexico, and concluded that the brachiopod shells have low preservation potential and are readily destroyed within days or months depending on burial mode unless the brachiopod shells become rapidly buried in beach ridges formed during catastrophic storm events. Although it is possible that thick-walled Paleozoic lingulide brachiopods might have had higher fossilization potential (Kowalewski, 1996), the sedimentary build-up of the lower Ordovician Kallavere Formation points to a storm-controlled deposition of the apatitic brachiopods to peritidal-to-shoreface settings, enabling the preservation of the brachiopod shells and creating a specific oxic-to-suboxic early diagenetic environment with low trace element concentrations limiting the diagenetic uptake of Cd, U and other trace elements.

Dynamic redox conditions during diagenesis are exemplified by different iron species found in the shelly phosphorites varying from the large accumulations of bleached pale yellowish to reddish beige shells in the Rakvere deposit deposited in nearshore-beach ridge settings to dark grey and black brachiopod shell detritus in Toolse and Aseri deposits (Lang et al., 2016; Lumiste et al., 2021a). The coloring of the brachiopod shells appears to be controlled by the presence and amount of authigenic pyrite in the lamellar structure of the brachiopod valves – dark grey to black shells and their fragments contain abundant authigenic pyrite (Fig. 2c-d), whereas lighter valves have scarce pyrite and may contain hematite instead (e.g., Lang et al., 2016). The hematite is likely not *sensu stricto* authigenic but replaces pyrite that was originally precipitated within an anoxic microenvironment inside the shell during the degradation of collagen and other organic matter (Canfield and Raiswell, 1991; Wings, 2004). During early diagenesis, such anoxic microenvironments created by decaying organic matter are largely decoupled from the redox conditions of the surrounding fluid (Pfretzschner, 2004). However, after the degradation of organic matter is completed, the redox conditions within the fossils equilibrate with the surrounding porewater (Pfretzschner and Tütken, 2011). The presence of hematite in the shells of the Rakvere deposit points towards oxic-to-suboxic conditions during diagenesis, leading to the oxidation of primary pyrite and the formation of secondary hematite within the shells. In contrast, the preservation of pyrite shells from deeper-water facies indicates persistently anoxic conditions during diagenesis.

Both the precipitation of authigenic apatite and the diagenesis of biogenic and authigenic apatite tend to occur under or at least transiently suboxic to sulfidic conditions (Arning et al., 2009b; Lumiste et al., 2021a, 2021b). These conditions favor the formation of pyrite and its enrichment of chalcophile elements like Zn, Cu, and Pb, as well as As and Cd. However, the thickest and the most P-rich beds of the Estonian shelly phosphorites, the Rakvere deposit, formed in oxic-to-suboxic shoreface environment and are comparably low in pyrite and associated heavy metals. Toolse and Aseri deposits, on the other hand, were likely deposited in a peritidal environment under more reducing conditions (Lumiste et al., 2021a) and are somewhat more enriched in several of the chalcophiles and U (Fig. 9).

Similarly, the uptake of REE + Y by apatite is primarily controlled by pore-water conditions, with reducing conditions leading to higher REE concentrations (e.g., Lumiste et al., 2019). There are notable differences in correlation between P_2O_5 and $\sum REE$ in different deposits. In Toolse and Aseri deposits, phosphorite P_2O_5 and $\sum REE$ show a high degree of correlation ($r > 0.9$, $p < 0.05$; Fig. 7); however, the covariation is absent in the Rakvere deposit phosphorite, where $\sum REE$ concentrations above 250 mg/kg are invariant with respect to P_2O_5 content (Fig. 7). This is likely due to the low degree of diagenetic enrichment of $\sum REE$ in shelly coquinas deposited at the shore/beach settings.

The REE uptake in apatite occurs during diagenetic processes through a pairwise substitution of two Ca^{2+} ions by one REE^{3+} and one monovalent ion or by substitution of Ca^{2+} and P^{5+} ions with REE^{3+} and Si^{4+} (Pan and Fleet, 2002). REE are supplied from the water column to the sediments by sinking organic matter and/or particulate Fe–Mn oxyhydroxides (Abbott et al., 2015). Degradation of organic matter and

reductive dissolution of Fe–Mn oxyhydroxides control the porewater REE levels and distribution (Haley et al., 2004). Sediments deposited in the beach zone were likely low in organic matter and Fe–Mn oxyhydroxides, resulting in low REE levels in porewater and apatite. Apatite in brachiopod shells of Rakvere deposit contains, on average, 235 mg/kg of $\sum\text{REE}$ (Lumiste et al., 2021a), only slightly higher than average shales ($\sum\text{REE}$ in PAAS = 183 mg/kg; Taylor and McLennan, 1985). In Toolse and Aseri deposits, the Kallavere Formation sandstones are characterized by more fine-grained sediments deposited in peritidal-distal lower shoreface to offshore environment. These deposits contain diagenetic pyrite and pyrite-bound trace elements (Fig. 9), indicating more reducing conditions (Lumiste et al., 2021a) and likely higher porewater REE concentrations due to higher rates of Fe–Mn oxyhydroxide and organic matter input, resulting in higher degree of REE-enrichment in apatite. Furthermore, REE + Y composition of the shells from the different deposits similarly points to varying conditions during early diagenesis, with higher Y/Ho and lower BSI values in Rakvere deposits, compared to Aseri and Toolse (Lumiste et al., 2021a).

Unlike most REEs, Ce is redox-sensitive and occurs in the insoluble tetravalent form under oxic conditions (Elderfield et al., 1981). Tetravalent Ce, compared with trivalent REE, is preferentially removed from the oxygenated water column by settling Fe–Mn-oxyhydroxide particles, causing a negative Ce anomaly in seawater, whereas the absence or a positive Ce anomaly would be characteristic of anoxic marine porewaters because of Ce released by the reductive dissolution of Ce carriers (Bau et al., 1997). In the shelly phosphorites, the variability in diagenetic redox conditions is suggested by a wide spread of Ce/Ce* values in the studied bulk sample dataset (Fig. 10), as well as by in-situ analyses of the brachiopod shells reported in Lumiste et al. (2021a). However, most of the Ce anomaly values do not classify as “true” Ce anomalies (sensu Bau and Dulski, 1996). None of the samples show true negative Ce anomalies that would be expected if the REE + Y uptake in shells had occurred directly from seawater. Instead, the absence of a Ce anomaly and an indication of true positive Ce anomaly in some of the analyzed samples suggest REE + Y uptake from a diagenetically modified porefluid.

An early diagenetic imprint on REE + Y composition of the phosphatic shells is also supported by La_N/Sm_N and La_N/Yb_N values (Fig. 11). The measured ratios largely overlap with modern marine pore fluid values, pointing towards a porewater source for the REE found in the apatite. The La_N/Yb_N values are similar across all deposits, ranging from ~0.5 to 1.2. In contrast, the La_N/Sm_N ratios vary between deposits. The La_N/Sm_N ratios of the Aseri shells are lower, with an average of 0.49 (SD = 0.07, $n = 31$), compared to 0.57 (SD = 0.1, $n = 123$) and 0.6 (SD = 0.07, $n = 63$) in Rakvere and Toolse, respectively. These higher values

Fig. 10. Ce-anomalies of the measured phosphorites and handpicked brachiopod shells. Modified after Bau and Dulski (1996). Data for the brachiopod shells from Lumiste et al. (2021a).

Fig. 11. Cross-plot of PAAS-normalized La/Yb and La/Sm values showing equal or slightly higher values than modern marine pore-fluids. Modified after Herwartz et al. (2013), with data from Deng et al. (2017); Goldstein and Jacobsen (1988); Haley et al. (2004); Kim et al. (2012); Lumiste et al. (2021a) and Reynard et al. (1999).

are caused by greater MREE enrichment in the Aseri shells, either because of apatite crystal-chemical controls leading to preferential incorporation of MREE (Reynard et al., 1999) or more MREE-enriched anoxic porewaters during diagenesis (sensu Kocsis et al., 2009; Ounis et al., 2008). However, given the relatively low $\sum\text{REE}$ values of the shells, coupled with high concentrations of terrigenous phases, the relative proportion of REE that were diagenetically sequestered by authigenic phases and REE sourced from terrigenous phases was likely roughly equal. As a result, REE-based proxies measured from bulk samples may not directly reflect the paleo-redox conditions in the Kallavere Formation.

Valetich et al. (2022) found that near-shore authigenic phosphorites are more REE-enriched compared to lower shelf deposits due to higher REE input from riverine and groundwater discharge, with the composition of basement rocks exerting first-order control on the REE concentrations in phosphorites. However, in the shelly phosphorites, the deposits formed in near-shore and/or shore settings (i.e., phosphorite in the Rakvere deposit) show lower degrees of REE enrichment. Furthermore, given the short distance – in the range of tens of kilometers – between the different deposits, it is unlikely that there would have been significant differences in the detrital-sourced REE. An alternative scenario explaining the lower REE + Y and other trace element content in shelly phosphorite – particularly in the Rakvere deposit, formed in a shore-face and/or beach setting – would imply secondary leaching processes under oxygenated conditions influencing the trace element content and distribution as hinted by secondary hematite within shells formed at the expense of pyrite. It is possible that REEs were leached from the shells during weathering, as percolating surface/meteoric waters are depleted of REEs compared to apatite phases (Shields and Stille, 2001). REE leaching induced by weathering causes REE fractionation because the relatively more stable La, Gd and Y are preferentially retained in the apatite during weathering, due to the tetrad effect (Bau and Dulski, 1996). Consequently, Y/Y^* and La_N/Nd_N values should increase during weathering (Shields and Stille, 2001), resulting in a positive correlation between the Y anomaly and La_N/Nd_N . However, shelly phosphorite samples from all three deposits show lower-than-marine Y/Y^* and La_N/Nd_N values (Fig. 12) suggesting that the samples are unaffected by weathering. Instead, the Y anomaly and La_N/Nd_N

Fig. 12. Cross-plot of Y-anomalies and PAAS-normalized La/Nd ratios, indicating a strong diagenetic influence on the phosphorite samples. The dashed line represents seawater values sensu Shields and Stille (2001).

relationship point to significant control by diagenetic uptake processes on the REE content in the phosphatic shells. Furthermore, a high concentration of Sr and its strong correlation with P_2O_5 (Fig. 5C, $r = 0.98$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 217$), the former being substituted for Ca^{2+} in the apatite structure similar to REE, suggests negligible leaching influence on the trace element composition of the studied shelly phosphorite.

5.3. Implications for REE and trace element enrichment in sedimentary phosphorites

Diagenetic uptake of trace elements by apatite occurs on short timescales near the SWI (Auer et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2023), and even relatively pristine authigenic chemically precipitated apatite grains can be significantly enriched in REE and other trace elements (Lumiste et al., 2019). Furthermore, the uptake of REE and U seems to be contemporaneous, indicating that early diagenesis exerts primary control on the trace elemental composition of apatite (Li et al., 2023). Although redox conditions influence both the input and dissolution of particle-bound REE, Cd availability and the speciation (and mobility) of U, it does not seem to be the primary factor controlling enrichment. Bioapatitic remains and authigenic apatite grains in deep-sea muds are highly enriched in REE, with concentrations 1–2 orders of magnitude higher than in typical phosphorites (Ren et al., 2022) and U enrichments covary positively with REE + Y (Li et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024b). Unlike shallower shelf-hosted phosphorites, where reducing conditions lead to a higher degree of REE enrichment compared to (sub)oxic sites (e.g., Lumiste et al., 2019), these sediments are formed under oxic-to-suboxic conditions (Bi et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2023; Kashiwabara et al., 2018), where porewater REE concentrations are lower (Deng et al., 2017; Haley et al., 2004) and should, therefore, lead to lower enrichment levels in apatite. However, these sediments are typified by near-zero or extremely low sedimentation rates, allowing prolonged uptake of trace elements from diagenetic porewaters or directly from seawater, where REE + Y can be sourced from mid-ocean ridge hydrothermal activity and transferred to sediments by Fe/Mn-oxhydroxide particles (Bi et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2023; Kato et al., 2011; Li et al., 2023; Ren et al., 2022; Takaya et al., 2018). Interestingly, similar to the shelly phosphorites, deep-sea muds seem to be depleted in U and Cd compared to average

phosphorites (Fig. 9), likely due to the low input of organic-bound Cd and relatively oxic diagenetic conditions present in deep-sea sediments. Similarly, the phosphogenic sediments containing authigenic apatite forming on continental shelf margins are typified by low or even negative rates of sedimentation (Föllmi, 1996). The shelly phosphorites were, on the other hand, formed under high-to-catastrophic sedimentation rates (i.e., storms and other high-energy events), allowing the preservation of brachiopod shell beds (Kowalewski, 1996) at beach ridges along the coastline, but cutting the shells off from (or limiting) contact with seawater during the early diagenetic recrystallization of bioapatite.

Given that trace element enrichment is tightly coupled to sedimentation rates (Klinkhammer and Palmer, 1991), showing (near-)linear negative correlations under reducing conditions (Liu and Algeo, 2020), the unique depositional environment of the shelly phosphorites might have exerted first-order control on the uptake of trace elements and led to low trace element levels in the brachiopod shells. Ultimately, sedimentation rates, coupled with redox conditions, primarily control the trace element uptake in sedimentary apatite.

6. Conclusions

We examined Cambrian-Ordovician shelly phosphorites of the Baltic Paleobasin in Estonia that, dissimilar to other large phosphorite deposits, are almost exclusively made up of phosphatic brachiopod shells. Dissimilar to other major phosphorite deposits, concentrations of potentially harmful metals (e.g., Cd, U) are exceptionally low, with Cd concentrations several orders of magnitude lower than in average phosphorites. The $\sum REE$ values are lower than global averages, but the shells are enriched in MREE. Furthermore, there are significant differences in the trace elements composition of the ores in different shelly phosphorite deposits. The variability is ultimately linked to the depositional environment. The most P-rich beds of the shelly phosphorite found in the Rakvere deposit are made up of planar and trough cross-bedded sandstone facies, which are interpreted to represent beach ridges formed during large catastrophic storm events. The fine-grained phosphatic sandstones of the Toolse and Aseri deposits, however, were deposited under peritidal shoreface to offshore environments.

Sedimentation rates and redox conditions in these two depositional environments differed significantly. The low trace element enrichment of the shelly phosphorites is likely caused by an interplay of different compounding factors of (i) the biogenic origin of the apatite leading to lower pre-diagenetic concentrations, (ii) oxygenated or less-reducing conditions leading to trace element depleted porewater during diagenesis and (iii) higher rates of sedimentation limiting the amount of time available for diagenetic mineral-water interaction. The compositional variability of the shelly phosphorite deposits further underlines the importance of these factors, with higher rates of sedimentation and less reducing diagenetic conditions of the shallower portion of the shelf (i.e., Rakvere deposit) corresponding to lower degrees of enrichment. Furthermore, our results have broader implications for the chemical composition of sedimentary phosphorites. Sedimentation rates seem to exert primary control on the trace element composition of apatite. Phosphorites deposited under low sedimentation rates and reducing diagenetic conditions are the most prospective for REE mineralization.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Karel Lumiste: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Johannes Vind:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Kairi Põldsaar:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Lauri Joosu:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Elina Kuusma:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Päärn Paiste:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Kalle Kirsimäe:**

Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2025.122776>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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